

Surviving case of Myocarditis Induced by Aluminium Phosphide Poisoning

Ketata Imen 1 ; Marwen Nadia 2 ; Khadhrani Manel 2 ; Soua Sarra 4; Chayeb Bassem 5 ;
Zguem Hadhami 3; Bouazizi Maha 6 ; Hamdi Malek 3 ; Bouhamed Chafiaa 1.

1. Hospital of IBN EL JAZZAR, emergency department, Kairouan, Tunisia
2. Hospital of IBN EL JAZZAR, Departement of gyneco obstetric , Kairouan, Tunisia

Corresponding author: Nadia Marwen

Received: Apr 29, 2025

Accepted: May 29, 2025

Published: Jun 10, 2025

Conflicts of interest and funding sources: No Conflicts of interest and no funding

Abstract

Introduction

Aluminium phosphide (AP) is a potent insecticide and rodenticide that can cause cellular damage, leading to multiorgan dysfunction and death. Intoxication occurs via ingestion or inhalation of phosphine gas, with potential fatalities within 12-24 hours due to cardiovascular toxicity. There is no effective antidote, and prognosis is largely dependent on cardiac damage, with mortality rates nearing 100% in severe cases.

Case report

We present a case of a 21-year-old female farmer with no significant medical history, admitted for respiratory distress and chest pain after ingesting 6 grams of aluminum phosphide in her first suicide attempt. Examination showed a Glasgow Coma Scale score of 14, 90% oxygen saturation, and lung crepitations. She had low blood pressure and signs of peripheral hypoperfusion.

The patient received oxygen therapy and isotonic serum. Noradrenaline was administered for hypotension, and an electrocardiogram revealed sinus tachycardia with transient ST segment elevation. Dobutamine was added. Initial lab tests indicated normal liver function, a prothrombin time of 31%, and elevated creatine kinase, lactate dehydrogenase, and troponin levels.

Arterial blood gas analysis showed metabolic acidosis and elevated lactate. Ultrasound revealed septal hypokinesia, a left ventricular ejection fraction of 30-35%, and Grade 2 mitral regurgitation. The diagnosis was acute toxic myocarditis with cardiogenic shock, leading to ICU transfer. The patient showed improvement and was discharged after seven days.

Conclusion:

Toxic myocarditis from AP intoxication is a critical and often fatal condition. Early intervention with inotropic and vasoactive agents can improve outcomes. A standardized treatment protocol is vital for enhancing survival rates and optimizing care.

Keys words: Aluminium phosphide; Myocarditis; Intoxication; Transthoracic ultrasound.

Introduction

Aluminium phosphide (AP) serves as a highly potent insecticide and rodenticide, extensively used in commercial agriculture, particularly within grain storage facilities.[1] Unlike targeting a single organ for damage, AP operates at the cellular level, causing widespread harm that results in multiorgan dysfunction (MOD) and eventual death.[1,2] Intoxication can occur through ingestion or inhalation of phosphine gas released by AP. It effectively serves as an autolysis agent. [1,2] Ingesting AP is severely debilitating, often leading to death within 12 to 24 hours, primarily due to imminent cardiovascular toxicity. Unfortunately, there is currently no effective treatment or specific antidote available for AP intoxication.[3] Prognosis mainly hinges on cardiac damage, with mortality rates nearing 100% in cases of severe cardiogenic shock [2].

Case report

We present the case of a young female patient, a 21-year-old farmer with no prior medical, cardiovascular, or psychiatric history. She was admitted to our emergency department with sudden onset respiratory distress and chest pain without radiation, following the voluntary ingestion of two pills (6 grams) of aluminum phosphide. This act was her first suicide attempt, prompted by family conflicts.

The physical examination revealed a Glasgow Coma Scale score of 14, intermediate-sized pupils, polypnea with oxygen saturation pulsating at 90%, crepitation, and rhonchi in both pulmonary bases. Blood pressure was measured at 60/40 with a mean arterial pressure of 47, while the pulse rate stood at 120 bpm, accompanied by signs of peripheral hypoperfusion including cold extremities and mottling.

In response, a 6-liter facial mask was applied for oxygen therapy, and the patient received 0.5 liters of isotonic serum. Due to refractory hypotension, subsequently, Noradrenaline was initiated intravenously via an electric syringe (IVSE) through a central venous catheter.

An electrocardiogram (EKG) (figure1) was promptly performed, revealing sinus tachycardia with a regular rhythm at 130 bpm, along with transient ST segment elevation in the anterior territory.

Figure 1 : An electrocardiogram (EKG)

Dobutamine was introduced alongside Noradrenaline at a rate of 15 gamma/kg/min, aiming to achieve a mean arterial pressure of 70 mmHg.

Initial laboratory tests revealed normal liver function, a spontaneously low prothrombin time of 31% without evidence of external bleeding, normal blood cell counts, creatine kinase (CPK) levels at 400 IU/L (normal range: 0-145), and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels at 250 IU/L (normal range: 0-147). High-sensitivity cardiac troponin was measured at 19.000 ug/L.

Arterial blood gas analysis indicated metabolic acidosis with a pH of 7.34, partial pressure of carbon dioxide (PaCO₂) at 29 mmHg, bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) level at 12 mmol/L, and partial pressure of oxygen (PaO₂) at 97 mmHg. Arterial lactate levels were recorded at 12 mmol/L.

Transthoracic ultrasound examination was performed (figure2), uncovering septal hypokinesia and a left ventricular systolic ejection fraction ranging between 30-35%.

Additionally, Grade 2 mitral regurgitation was noted, with no significant aortic pathology observed, and preserved right ventricular function evident. Notably, the pericardium appeared unremarkable without any signs of effusion or inflammation.

Figure 2 : Transthoracic ultrasound examination

Based on these findings, a diagnosis of acute toxic myocarditis complicated by cardiogenic shock was established, prompting the immediate transfer of the patient to the intensive care unit (ICU).

The patient's condition showed improvements over time, including resolution of metabolic acidosis, clearance of lactate, and gradual reduction in Noradrenaline infusion by day five. Ultrasound assessment on the fourth day revealed an estimated ejection fraction (EF) of 35%. Dobutamine administration was discontinued by the fifth day, and the patient's need for supplemental oxygen ceased. Following a seven-day ICU admission and psychiatric consultation, the patient was discharged home.

Discussion:

Aluminium Phosphide poisoning is a rodenticide commonly used for self-poisoning in parts of Central Asia, including India and Iran [2]. A lethal dose for an adult is between 0.15 and 0.5 g [2]. Upon contact with water, humidity, or stomach contents, it produces phosphine gas (PH₃) [1,2]. Its primary mode of action is thought to be the inhibition of cytochrome oxidase, which impairs cellular oxygen utilization in various organs, especially the heart, lungs, liver, and kidneys [1,2].

This leads to refractory cardiogenic shock and metabolic acidosis.

Myocardial damage is observed in 60% to 100% of cases of ALP intoxication. It can present as pericarditis, myocarditis, new-onset heart failure, subendocardial infarction, refractory hypotension, and shock. [4]

Electrocardiographic (ECG) abnormalities are observed in approximately 85% of patients with ALP poisoning and are indicative of a poor prognosis [4,5]. The most common abnormality is ST-segment elevation, which can mimic acute myocardial infarction, particularly involving the inferior and lateral leads [5].

The most common etiology of ST segment elevation and raised troponins is acute coronary syndrome. However, these findings in the setting of ALP poisoning don't warrant use of antiplatelets, anticoagulants or thrombolytics therapy. The mechanism is not acute atherothrombosis of coronary artery but ALP induced myocardial injury.

In fact, Aluminium phosphide in the presence of moisture and/or gastric hydrochloric acid release phosphine gas. Phosphine inhibits the catalase, cytochrome c oxidase (ETC) and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) activity in cardiac myocytes. It disrupts the mitochondrial function, decrease in overall ATP production, and reduces myocardial energy. G6PD inhibition reduces glutathione concentration. Free radicles especially ROS and oxidative stress lead to lipid peroxidation and lead to cardiac toxicity and multiorgan failure[4] . The Molecular Mechanism of Aluminum Phosphide poisoning in Cardiovascular Disease: Pathophysiology and Diagnosti

Another electric abnormality was found in our study was Sinus tachycardia which in literature ,typically appears within the first three to six hours of poisoning, followed by ST-T changes and conduction disturbances between hours six and twelve, and eventually, arrhythmias [6]. Research indicates that ventricular tachycardia occurs in 40% of cases, ventricular fibrillation in 23.3%, supraventricular tachycardia in 46.7%, and atrial flutter/fibrillation in 20% of ALP-poisoned patients[7].

Additional ECG findings such as a QRS width greater than 120 ms, atrioventricular block, symptomatic bradycardia or tachycardia, and ventricular arrhythmias should heighten suspicion of acute myocarditis (AM) and suggest a high-risk condition. [8]

While second- or third-degree atrioventricular block is uncommon in patients with a normal left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) greater than 50% [5,9].

Recommended laboratory tests for identification of patients with suspected AM are myocardial necrosis biomarkers (high-sensitivity troponins, creatinine kinase-MB). Only a weak correlation exists between troponin release and the severity of cardiac dysfunction. Other laboratory tests routinely requested include markers of inflammation such as C-reactive protein that is positive in 80% to 95%.

The management of ACP typically prioritizes early resuscitation with crystalloids and inotropic agents. Hydroxyethyl starch (HES) may be considered for initial hypotension management before the administration of vasopressors, though this approach remains debated [10,11].

Tri-iodothyronine (T3) has demonstrated efficacy in rat models of phosphine-induced myocarditis at a dose of 3 µg/kg, significantly improving ECG patterns and oxidative stress markers. Additionally, T3 may enhance mitochondrial function and ATP production in cardiac cells, thereby improving cellular viability. However, its clinical application in humans has yet to be explored [12]

Digoxin, although known to improve cardiac output, reduce pulmonary capillary pressure and heart rate, and positively influence the neurohormonal profile, is not formally indicated for myocarditis of this etiology [13]

N-acetylcysteine (NAC), a potent antioxidant that facilitates intracellular glutathione regeneration, has shown cardioprotective potential in animal studies by mitigating phosphine-induced oxidative stress in cardiac cells. Nevertheless, a 2016 case-control study by Taghaddosinejad found no significant effect on mortality [14].

Hyperinsulinemia/euglycemia therapy has also shown potential in phosphine-induced myocarditis by improving cardiac inotropy, likely through metabolic modulation and restoration of calcium flux [15].

Trimetazidine, an anti-ischemic agent with cardioprotective properties, has been suggested for the management of toxic myocarditis. It preserves oxidative metabolism, reduces tissue malondialdehyde levels—a marker of lipid peroxidation—and enhances intracellular ATP

levels. While it has been used in isolated cases without severe symptoms [16], its routine use in all cases of toxic myocarditis is not currently recommended.

Specific guidelines for the management of phosphine cardiac toxicity and duration of the treatment are still lacking ,that's why we tend to report new cases and their developments in order to ensure better care and improve their prognosis.

Conclusion:

Toxic myocarditis due to PAL intoxication represents a critical and often fatal condition, particularly without a structured therapeutic strategy in an intensive care setting. However, early and targeted intervention, including the swift administration of inotropic and vasoactive agents, combined with echocardiographic guidance and frequent blood volume monitoring, can markedly improve outcomes. The establishment of a codified treatment protocol is imperative to enhance survival rates and optimize patient care.

Bibliography:

1. Mehrpour O, Jafarzadeh M, Abdollahi M. A Systematic Review of Aluminium Phosphide Poisoning. *Arhiv za higijenu rada i toksikologiju*. 21 mars 2012;63(1):61-72.
2. Singh Y, Joshi SC, Satyawali V, Gupta A. Acute aluminium phosphide poisoning, what is new? *Egypt J Intern Med*. 1 sept 2014;26(3):99-103.
3. Anand R, Binukumar BK, Gill KD. Aluminum phosphide poisoning: an unsolved riddle. *Journal of Applied Toxicology*. 2011;31(6):499-505.
4. Petrovic M, Otero D, Leigh A, Singh V. Acute Heart Failure Due to Aluminum Phosphide Poisoning. 9 sept 2021;17(3):6.
5. Ammirati E, Frigerio M, Adler ED, Basso C, Birnie DH, Brambatti M, et al. Management of Acute Myocarditis and Chronic Inflammatory Cardiomyopathy. *Circulation: Heart Failure* [Internet]. nov 2020 [cité 5 févr 2024]; Disponible sur: <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/abs/10.1161/CIRCHEARTFAILURE.120.007405>
6. Katira R, Elhence GP, Mehrotra ML, Srivastava SS, Mitra A, Agarwala R, et al. A study of aluminum phosphide (AIP) poisoning with special reference to electrocardiographic changes. *J Assoc Physicians India*. juill 1990;38(7):471-3.
7. Siwach SB, Singh H, Jagdish null, Katyal VK, Bhardwaj G. Cardiac arrhythmias in aluminium phosphide poisoning studied by on continuous holter and cardioscopic monitoring. *J Assoc Physicians India*. juill 1998;46(7):598-601.
8. Gupta MS, Malik A, Sharma VK. Cardiovascular manifestations in aluminium phosphide poisoning with special reference to echocardiographic changes. *J Assoc Physicians India*. nov 1995;43(11):773-4, 779-80.
9. Elgazzar FM, Shama MA, Shoeib O, Hafez ASAF. The Role of Echocardiographic Findings in Estimating Survival Probability of Intensive Care Unit Admitted Aluminum Phosphide Poisoned Patients. *J Med Toxicol*. avr 2022;18(2):128-38.
10. Kafi G, Akbarpour S, Arefi M, Behnoush B, Ahmadi Pishkuhi M, Barzegari N. Effect of hydroxyethyl starch on acidosis in patients with aluminum phosphide poisoning. *Caspian J Intern Med*. 2019;10(3):271-5.
11. Farahani MV, Soroosh D, Marashi SM. Thoughts on the current management of acute aluminum phosphide toxicity and proposals for therapy: An Evidence-based review. *Indian J Crit Care Med*. déc 2016;20(12):724-30.
12. Abdolghaffari AH, Baghaei A, Solgi R, Gooshe M, Baeri M, Navaei-Nigjeh M, et al. Molecular and biochemical evidences on the protective effects of triiodothyronine against phosphine-induced cardiac and mitochondrial toxicity. *Life Sciences*. 15 oct 2015;139:30-9.
13. Mehrpour O, Farzaneh E, Abdollahi M. Successful Treatment of Aluminum Phosphide Poisoning with Digoxin: A Case Report and Review of Literature. *International Journal of Pharmacology*. 1 juill 2011;7:761-4.

14. Taghaddosinejad F, Farzaneh E, Ghazanfari-Nasrabad M, Eizadi-Mood N, Hajhosseini M, Mehrpour O. The effect of N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) on aluminum phosphide poisoning inducing cardiovascular toxicity: a case-control study. Springerplus. 10 nov 2016;5(1):1948.
15. Hassanian-Moghaddam H, Zamani N. Therapeutic role of hyperinsulinemia/euglycemia in aluminum phosphide poisoning. Medicine. août 2016;95(31):e4349.
16. Dueñas A, Pérez-Castrillon JL, Cobos MA, Herreros V. Treatment of the cardiovascular manifestations of phosphine poisoning with trimetazidine, a new antiischemic drug. Am J Emerg Med. mars 1999;17(2):219-20.